

Relationship between chlorophyll fluorescence (Fv/Fm) measured after 5 d of chilling treatment at 17 °C and spikelet sterility (%) for 8 rice genotypes. Pokhara, Nepal.

therefore used as a good diagnostic probe for measuring cold stress. A healthy leaf generally gives a Fv/Fm value of about 0.80.

We grew the rice genotypes under glasshouse conditions (28/18 °C) until the booting stage. Plants were chilled for 5 d at 17 °C under a 10/14 h day/night cycle in a growth chamber, taken back to the glasshouse, and kept there at 23 °C to complete the crop cycle. Plants were given plant food Champax Formula No. 2 at 0.714 g/liter of tap water.

We measured chlorophyll fluorescence of the flag leaves after 5 d of chilling using a CF1000 fluorometer. Panicle sterility and other agronomic parameters were measured at harvest.

A significant negative correlation ($r = -0.89$) between Fv/Fm at booting and spikelet sterility (%) was found (see figure). This indicates that Fv/Fm can be used to predict spikelet fertility and is therefore a useful tool in screening for cold tolerance at anthesis.

Cold-tolerant varieties Silange, Chhomrong, Sinjali, Kalopatie, and Takmare had higher photochemical efficiency under chilling stress and the least spikelet sterility of the varieties tested. Cold-sensitive cultivars, such as Marshi, had smaller Fv/Fm values and the greatest degree of sterility (56.3%). Darmali and Bhatte, both known for cold tolerance at tillering, exhibited poor tolerance at anthesis (see figure).

Results from both field and growth chamber experiments suggest that relative ranking for cold tolerance can be based on absolute Fv/Fm values recorded after cold stress.

Further studies are planned in Nepal using this technique to study cold tolerance in segregating populations and in the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery. ■

reaction centers photosystem II (PSII). The onset of chilling injury in leaves is accompanied by a decrease in chlorophyll fluorescence. The ratio of variable fluorescence (Fv) to maximal fluorescence (Fm), termed as photochemical efficiency of PSII (Fv/Fm), is directly related to its quantum efficiency and is

Efficiency of natural selection against cold-induced sterility in bulked families

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ISABU identified Yunnan 3 in 1980 as a relatively well-adapted variety for swamps at 1,300 to 1,650 m above sea level (m asl). Growing rice at this altitude is important for Burundi as it is a densely

populated country (206 humans/km²). International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery results, however, were disappointing. A breeding program was initiated to improve varietal diversification.

The isotherms of the area vary between 16 and 22 °C with frequent night temperatures as low as 10 °C. Cold-induced sterility is the major constraint.

We bulked reciprocal crosses in rapid generations at 800 m asl. Some families (Facagro 57 and Facagro 59) with narrow variability were subjected to natural selection in F₄₋₆ at 1,550 m asl at the 16 °C isotherm. The yields of the Facagro 57 and 59 families progressed annually,

Sterility of families derived from 2 hybrids subjected to natural selection from F₄ to F₆ at 16 °C isotherm.

partly because of lowered sterility. Facagro 57 originated from B2980b-Sr-2-6-2-3-2/IR24312-RR-19-3-B (45.7 and 83.7% parental sterility, respectively). Facagro 59 originated from IR24312-RR-19-3-B/NR10041-66-3-1 (83.7 and 70.8% parental sterility, respectively).

Sterility was estimated using a sample of 25 disease-free panicles (three replications) from the same site in a pluriannual trial that included Ambalalava, a well-adapted variety at 1,500 to 1,700 m asl in Madagascar.

The figure illustrates the evolution of sterility. F₄₋₆ trials showed sterility levels below that of Ambalalava.

The level attained in 1991 is one of normal sterility, showing the polygenic nature of cold tolerance that prolonged action until F₈; the parents are evidently not adapted, but they are good breeding lines for cold tolerance.

The bulk population method is efficient for determining this kind of selection. ■